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Sol2H2O

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1. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of Sol2H2O¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable D3.3 - Career attractiveness framework report, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

This Deliverable reports on the implementation and impacts of career attractiveness support measures:

- ERC Facility: description of support assets, identified candidates for Advanced and Synergy Grants, abstract of submitted proposals, outcome of submitted proposals;
- Spin-Off facility: description of support assets, asset matrix per partner, IP paths and foreseeable costs, company creation path and foreseeable costs and incentives, HR rules for transition to Spin-Off, Spin-Off creation framework in UEvora, blueprint for creation of spin-off (based on JRA result or on virtual result inspired in JRA);
- Living Amenities Facility: description of approach (web based platform), description of related initiatives, statistics, satisfaction inquiries, replication in TOP partners.

The activities described in this D3.3 are within the framework of Work Package (WP) 3.

2. CAREER ATTRACTIVENESS IN THE FRAMEWORK OF SOL2H2O PROJECT

Addressing one of the objectives of Sol2H2O, “3. To steer Career Building and attractiveness of Young Researchers to UEvora”, different support measures have been implemented in the project, aiming at a holistic approach to an attractiveness framework able to create lasting impacts in the Widening institution.

Rendering the Widening institution - the University of Évora - attractive to young researchers and, especially, creating an attractiveness framework, is surely related to the quality of research and research infrastructure therein available, but encompasses also other research unrelated aspects pertaining to the institution, the city, and the region.

Whereas research related aspects have been addressed by specific support actions on:

- capacity building, with Sol2H2O Fast-Track Schools (see related Deliverable 3.1);

¹ Project: 101079303 — SALTOpower — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

- tutoring and mentoring of PhD students and young researchers (see related Deliverable 3.2);
- fostering young researchers into leadership positions, with the development of the ERC Facility,

all of them grounded in Sol2H2O concrete research focus and on its Joint Research Activity, an additional set of support actions has been envisaged as to widen Sol2H2O attractiveness framework.

An assessment of “regional attractiveness” indicators to the region where the Widening institution is located² provides an interesting starting point. The definition of ‘regional attractiveness’ indicators has been developed as a tool for analysing the structural reasons for unequal development between regions, at supra- and infra-national level. Going beyond the criteria used in different methodologies for establishing these indicators, centred on parameters such as Foreign Direct Investment, the export index or the ‘brain drain’, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) recently developed a holistic methodology for quantifying a Regional Attractiveness Index (RAI). Based on six core dimensions - Economic Attractiveness, Natural Environment, Connectivity, Residents' Well-being, Space and Housing, Visitor Attractiveness - this methodology produces results relating to the attractiveness of three types of agents: Investors, Visitors and Talent³.

Taking the attractiveness index produced by this methodology as a starting point for a general assessment of the territory as an attractor of investment and talent (not neglecting the dimension of Visitors as an element of diversity and valorisation of heritage assets normally associated with tourism activity), the Better Life Index (BLI) also produced by the OECD⁴, provides an indication of the quality of life of residents.

Aimed at comparing conditions of ‘well-being’ between countries, this index is based on eleven parameters in the field of material conditions and quality of life: housing, income, employment, community, education, environment, civic participation, health, personal satisfaction, security and work-life balance.

In this study², the results obtained for the RAI and BLI serve as the basis for an analysis of the region's deficits in a) attracting and b) retaining talent, not only for the Alentejo region, but also for the neighbouring regions, possibly competing for talent: the Metropolitan Region of Lisbon and the Algarve.

Results for the different parameters assessed in each of these indicators, for both Alentejo and the neighbouring (competing) regions, are summarized in Figure 2.1.

This study shows the region's competitive advantages over its competitors:

- the natural environment/environment and;
- space/security and housing conditions,

aspects that will need to be highlighted and capitalised on, pointing out as disadvantages:

- the economic attractivity;
- the well-being of residents / civic participation, education, health;
- connectivity/access to services and;
- the attractiveness of visitors / cultural offer.

² Horta, P., Rosmaninho N., “Atractividade de Recursos Humanos Qualificados para a Região do Alentejo: aspectos críticos para uma estratégia de atractividade regional” (*Attractiveness of Qualified Human Resources to the Alentejo Region: critical aspects for a regional attractiveness strategy*). Public Policy Portuguese Journal, Volume 8, Number 2 (2023). University of Évora, UMPP.

³ OECD Regional Development Papers No. 36: Measuring the attractiveness of regions. OECD, 2022. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1787/fbe44086-en>

⁴ OECD Better Life Index. <https://www.oecdbetterlifeindex.org>

□ PT18: Alentejo
 □ PT17: Área Metropolitana de Lisboa
 □ PT15: Algarve

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.1: Classification on the different parameters of (a) Regional Attractiveness Index (RAI)⁵ and (b) Better Life Index (BLI)⁶ for the regions of Alentejo and Algarve compared to the reference Lisbon Metropolitan Area (Ref.100)

⁵ *TRACT. ECONÓMICA*: economic attractiveness; *AMBIENTE NATURAL*: natural environment; *CONECTIVIDADE*: connectivity; *BEM-ESTAR RESID.*: residents well being; *ESPAÇO E HABITAÇÃO*: site and housing; *TRACT. VISITANTES*: attractiveness to visitors

⁶ *Habitação*: housing; *Acesso a serviços*: access to services; *Segurança*: safety; *Satisfação pessoal*: personal satisfaction; *Saúde*: Health; *Participação Cívica*: civil participation; *Meio Ambiente*: Environment; *Comunidade*: community; *Educação*: education; *Emprego*: employment; *Rendimento*: income

Addressing (at least some of) these dimensions of attractiveness, Sol2H2O encompassed additional support measures, such as the development of:

- the “Spin-off Facility”, aiming at improving economic attractiveness conditions by means of supporting an “entrepreneurship path” to the further development of young researchers' careers by means of their exploitation of research results;
- the “Living Amenities Facility”, aiming at improving well being, access to services and cultural offer aspects or at capitalizing the region’s advantages on natural environment or space, security and housing conditions.

3. CAPACITY BUILDING

Capacity building activities within Sol2H2O included not only training activities, in the form of “Fast-Track Schools” aimed not only at CYR and YR but also to Industry engineers and technicians, but also Tutoring activities, aimed at supporting the development of PhD works by CYR, and Mentoring activities, aimed at supporting the career development of YR including at the development of leadership skills. These activities have been supported by Mobility activities, promoting the exchange of CYR and YR among the research infrastructure of all the partners in the Consortium.

3.1. Fast-track Schools

Aimed not only at CYR and YR but also at Industry engineers and technicians, the three editions of the Fast-track Schools (FTS), duly reported in Sol2H2O D3.1, were an evolutionary training along the project focused on the following main content approach:

- **FTS#1:** Basic research topics and State of the Art (SoA) contents on solar-driven water production & water treatment technologies and brine treatment processes, also including beyond SoA possibilities, in January 2024, at the University of Palermo, with 42 attendees;
- **FTS#2:** Experimental procedures and implementation, Beyond SoA (implementation, experimental campaigns, monitoring and data assessment), in September 2024, in the Canary Islands Institute of Technology, with 42 attendees (Figure 3.2);
- **FTS#3:** Technology benchmarking and Exploitation contents, in February 2025, at the University of Évora, with 32 attendees (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.2: FTS #2 - Pozo Izquierdo

Figure 3.3: FTS #3 - Évora

Satisfaction surveys delivered to the attendees in the three editions of the FTS showed an overall satisfaction rate of 4.66 out of 5.

FTS materials are publicly available and described on Deliverable 3.1 - Fast-Track School Materials.

3.2. Tutoring and mentoring

Task 3.2 Tutoring, led by CIEMAT, to support the Candidate Young Researchers (CYRs) to develop a PhD thesis in the scope of Sol2H2O, including CYR mobilities from the Widening partner (UÉvora) to the TOP partners (CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA) in a total of 5,76 weeks by M29. Nine CYRs have been engaged in the project, as presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Engagement of CYR in Sol2H2O

Partner	CYR name	PhD topic [JRA Task and guidance]	Tutor [Partner] Co-tutor [Partner]
UEVORA	Frederico Felizardo	Optimizing Solar-driven Water Production and Brine Valorization for Sustainable Solutions	Pedro Horta [UEVORA] Andrea Cipolina [UNIPA] Baltasar Peñate [ITC] Guillermo Zaragoza [CIEMAT]
UEVORA	Nuno Moreira	Solar-driven wastewater treatment technologies for removal of contaminants of emerging concern (CEC)	Maria Helena Novais [UEVORA] Isabel Oller [CIEMAT] José Eduardo Castanheiro [UEVORA]
UEVORA	Ricardo Silva	tbd	
CIEMAT	Isabel Requena	Batch operating solar membrane distillation systems for concentration of brines	Guillermo Zaragoza [CIEMAT] Juan Antonio Andrés Mañas [CIEMAT]
CIEMAT	Paula Serrano	Industrial wastewater regeneration and recovery of added-value substances	Isabel Oller [CIEMAT] Ana Ruiz Delgado [CIESOL (UAL-CIEMAT)]
ITC	Angel Rivero	Viability and applicability of SWRO brine valorisation processes in the Canary Islands	Baltasar Peñate Suárez (ITC) M ^a Concepción Fi-Fi Ling Ling (ULPGC)
UNIPA	Giuseppe Scelfo	Valorization of Seawater Waste Brines by Recovering Trace Element	Giorgio Micale [UNIPA] Alessandro Tombutini [UNIPA] Fabrizio Vicari [ResourSEAs]

Partner	CYR name	PhD topic [JRA Task and guidance]	Tutor [Partner] Co-tutor [Partner]
UNIPA	Lorenzo Ventimiglia	Innovative processes for brine valorization	Giorgio Micale [UNIPA]
UNIPA	Ferdinando Miciletta	Development of innovative technologies for the production of magnesium hydroxide from saline solutions	Alessandro Tombutini [UNIPA] Fabrizio Vicari [ResourSEAs]

Task 3.3 Mentoring, led by UNIPA, supports Young Researchers (YR) engaged in Sol2H2O JRA and FTS, aiming at their career development towards team leaders/leading researchers in the Sol2H2O field, including mobilities of UÉvora YR to TOP partners of 1.62 weeks by M29. Table 3.2 summarizes the Sol2H2O YR engagement.

Table 3.2: Engagement of YR in Sol2H2O

Partner	YR name	JRA Task	Mentor at Host Mentor [Partner]
UEVORA	Maria Helena Novais	T2.2	Pedro Horta [UEVORA] Isabel Oller [CIEMAT]
UNIPA	Nunzio Cancilla	T2.1	Andrea Cipollina [UNIPA] Guillermo Zaragoza [CIEMAT]
UNIPA	Antonia Filingeri	T2.1	Andrea Cipollina [UNIPA] Guillermo Zaragoza [CIEMAT]
CIEMAT	Ana Ruiz-Delgado	T2.2	Isabel Oller [CIEMAT] Andrea Cipollina [UNIPA]
CIEMAT	Alba Ruiz-Aguirre	T2.1	Guillermo Zaragoza [CIEMAT] Pedro Horta [UEVORA]

A survey was conducted during the last project meetings to assess the Sol2H2O team's satisfaction, and a total of 6 answers were received from CYR and YR. Table 3.3 presents some of the more relevant questions answered by CYR and YR, and to which they gave a score from 1 to 5 where: 1 means "I'm completely unsatisfied", 2 means "I'm partially unsatisfied", 3 means "I'm not satisfied or unsatisfied", 4 means "I'm partially satisfied" and 5 means "I completely satisfied".

Table 3.3: Sol2H2O CYR and YR answers to the satisfaction survey

Question	Classification (out of 5)
How satisfied are you with Sol2H2O research?	4,83
How satisfied are you with the support for career development at your institution?	4,67
How satisfied are you with the Sol2H2O Research Infrastructure?	4,50
How satisfied are you with the Sol2H2O team?	5,00
How satisfied are you with Sol2H2O in general?	4,83

Adding to mentoring activities aimed at YR, leadership training has also been sought to provide YR with tools and resources supporting the objective of hosting their careers to a group leadership position.

A 1-hour leadership training was held in the project meeting #4 (September 2024, in Pozo Izquierdo), by Juan Ferrer Cárdenes (www.juanferrer.es), consultant, trainer and speaker specialising in Change Management in organisations wishing to evolve and innovate. The presentation was untitled “The organizations that will build the future”, with the program:

- What are the organizations that build the future?
- What kind of leadership is necessary for the future?
- What’s the difference between Managing and Leading?
- Has the team got a leader? Or is the team the leader?
- Managers: how should they change the way they think?.

A leadership training also took place with the UÉvora team, including Sol2H2O's YR and CYR, in May 2025 (Figure 3.2.3). The programme is presented in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4: Program of Leadership Training to UEvora YR and CYR

06.05.2025		
9:00 - 9:30	Welcome and Introduction	Objectives: Introduction of the training and the participants Topics: Training objectives, agenda, introduction of participants
9:30 - 10:30	Activity 1 - Leadership Styles	Objectives: To identify each participant's leadership style and understand how it impacts the team. Topics: 4 classic leadership styles
10:30 - 11:15	Activity 2 - Task prioritisation	Objectives: Organise and prioritise tasks with a simple and intuitive matrix Topics: Eisenhower matrix
11:15 - 11:30	Break	
11:30 - 12:30	Activity 3 - Delegating with Efficiency and Confidence	Objectives: To delegate tasks effectively, ensuring quality results. Topics: Introduction to the principles of delegating tasks, RACI matrix
12:30 - 13:30	Lunch	
13:30 - 14:30	Activity 4 - Aligning Expectations and Feedback	Objectives: Improve communication and alignment between leadership and the team Topics: Guided role play of scenarios proposed by the participants.
14:30 - 15:15	Activity 5 - Motivation and Emotional Intelligence	Objectives: Identify factors that motivate the team and learn how to use them strategically Topics: Emotional intelligence and its impact on individual and team motivation
15:15 - 15:30	Break	
15:30 - 16:30	Activity 6 - Conflict Resolution in Practice	Objectives: To explore techniques for resolving conflicts constructively Topics: Conflict resolution
16:30 - 17:00	Closing and Final Reflection	Objectives: Reflection on the training and definition of next steps Topics: Making the connection between training content and practical work

Figure 3.2.3: Sol2H2O team in the leadership training in Évora

By the end of the training, a satisfaction survey was applied, with 11 answers, some of the answers are presented in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4: Answers to the leadership training satisfaction survey

Question	Classification
Do you believe the knowledge gained is applicable to your professional context?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Not at all ● Slightly ● Applicable ● Very applicable
Did the training contribute to your development as a leader/researcher?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strongly disagree ● Disagree ● Agree ● Strongly agree

4. ERC FACILITY

Regarded as one of the most prestigious career development support schemes for researchers in the European space, the Research Grants of the European Research Council⁷ are organized in four main categories following different career stages:

- ERC Starting Grant, for researchers with 2 to 7 years of postdoctoral experience;
- ERC Consolidator Grant, for researchers with 7 to 12 years of postdoctoral experience;
- ERC Advanced Grant, for established research leaders, and;
- ERC Synergy Grant, for groups of 2 to 4 researchers combining skills and resources, tackling ambitious research challenges.

In the framework of Sol2H2O, the application to ERC Grants has been sought as an instrument for exercising Young Researchers in the development of a career development plan, aiming at their future leadership of a research team developing activities aligned with the objectives of the Sol2H2O Joint Research Activity.

To this end, information on ERC Grant applications has been conveyed, from a early stage in the project, to the Young Researchers engaged in the project, namely on available calls and proposal templates, besides due discussion of possible topics and development of proposals along the Mentoring activities and mobility actions developed in the project (Task 3.2).

Moreover, at the Widening institutions' side, YRs have been made acquainted with a specific support program recently made available through the Portuguese National Contact Point institution, FCT - Science and Technology Foundation, FCT's ERC Portugal Program⁸.

Aiming at increasing the national participation in the ERC Calls, this program provides support for the different stages of proposal submission: from preparing and evaluating applications, to training future applicants and attracting and retaining talent. The program has three axes: ERC-PT Pre-assessment, ERC-PT A-Projects and ERC-PT Careers.

ERC-PT Pre-assessment supports the national scientific community in preparing proposals to the ERC. It consists of a pre-assessment by peers at the proposal preparation stage, following

⁷ <https://erc.europa.eu/apply-grant>

⁸ <https://www.fct.pt/en/financiamento/programas-de-financiamento/programa-erc-portugal/>

international best practice and according to the ERC's assessment criteria. The process is conducted by a College of international evaluators, appointed annually and covering all scientific areas, with highly experienced profiles in evaluation processes, preferably with experience of several editions as ERC panel members. It culminates in suggestions for improving the proposal, which reflect the ERC's evaluation criteria and evaluator profiles. This axis has supported national applications in 3 ERC Calls. Despite being a very recent program, it already has applications that have been selected for funding or have reached the second stage of the evaluation process.

ERC-PT A-Projects, the first axis launched under this program, is an FCT funding line for national applications with a top evaluation and recommendation for funding by the ERC, but which do not obtain funding due to budget limitations. Applications with an 'A' rating in the Starting, Consolidator and Advanced grants typologies are eligible for this funding, and, from October 2024, also Synergy grants. This financial support, up to a maximum of 250,000 euros per application, is intended to enable the institutions of the National Science and Technology System (SNCT) and their researchers for future ERC applications. The application period is open until December 31, 2025.

ERC-PT Careers, launched in June 2024, promotes the attraction and retention of researchers with projects funded by ERC Calls, still in progress or completed in less than 2 years, for permanent positions in SNCT and Higher Education institutions. This axis is made up of two types: (i) ATTRACT, with funding of up to 550,000 euros, to host projects that are transferred from foreign institutions through open-ended contracts with their principal investigators; (ii) RETAIN, an incentive to recruit researchers already carrying out research in Portugal and with an ERC project active or completed less than 2 years ago, for permanent positions in SNCT or Higher Education institutions.

ERC-PT A Projects and ERC-PT Careers are funded by the Recovery and Resilience Plan (PRR), in the resilience dimension and in the "RE-C06-i06 - Science Plus Capacity Building" component.

Finally, an ERC Synergy Grant proposal has been sought as an instrument to align ideas and structure a follow-up strategy to Sol2H2O scientific cooperation and research infrastructure development among Senior Researchers.

To this end, a number of specific meetings among Senior Researchers engaged in the project has been developed, aiming at identifying a suitable - and eligible - proposal encompassing not only the researchers' background complementarities but also the infrastructural synergies found among the Consortium partners.

4.1 ERC Starting Grant applications

Considering the eligibility criteria for applicants to ERC Starting Grants - researchers with 2 to 7 years of postdoctoral experience - the eligibility of Young Researchers enrolled in Sol2H2O JRA, on the side of each of the Consortium partners, was checked, as illustrated in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Eligibility of YR in Sol2H2O to ERC Starting Grant applications

Partner	YR name	JRA Task	Mentor at Host Mentor [Partner]	PhD year	Eligibility
UEVORA	Maria Helena Novais	T2.2	Pedro Horta [UEVORA] Isabel Oller [CIEMAT]	2011	N
UNIPA	Nunzio Cancilla	T2.1	Andrea Cipollina [UNIPA] Guillermo Zaragoza [CIEMAT]	2022	Y
UNIPA	Antonia Filingeri	T2.1	Andrea Cipollina [UNIPA] Guillermo Zaragoza [CIEMAT]	2024	N

Partner	YR name	JRA Task	Mentor at Host Mentor [Partner]	PhD year	Eligibility
CIEMAT	Ana Ruiz-Delgado	T2.2	Isabel Oller [CIEMAT] Andrea Cipollina [UNIPA]	2019	Y
CIEMAT	Alba Ruiz-Aguirre	T2.1	Guillermo Zaragoza [CIEMAT] Pedro Horta [UEVORA]	2017	N

Out of the two eligible YRs, and in fulfilment of the project target of 1 ERC Starting Grant proposals, one ERC Starting Grant application has already been submitted to the 2024 Call.

Sol2H2O YR Nunzio Cancilla has submitted an ERC Starting Grant proposal on 14 October 2024, after the description in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Summary of ERC Starting Grant application by Nunzio Cancilla (UNIPA YR)

Call	
Applicant name	Nunzio Cancilla
Title	Greenhouse Renewable Energy and Environmental Nexus with Water-from-Air Technology for Efficient Resources - GREENWATER
Abstract	The increasing global demand for food and water, along with the urgent need for sustainable agricultural practices, underscores the growing importance of seeking innovative solutions in the management of water resources. The GREENWATER project aims to develop an integrated system that harnesses innovative technologies for harvesting water from the air to generate freshwater for greenhouse irrigation. These technologies will provide an untapped resource for regions facing water scarcity. The harvested water will be used to irrigate crops in a controlled environment, ensuring efficient water use and contributing to sustainable food production. The system will be powered by renewable solar energy sources, enhancing both the overall process sustainability and the agricultural productivity while reducing reliance on fossil fuels. The objective of the GREENWATER project is to optimize the integration between the membrane unit for air-water capture and greenhouse horticulture, with the goal of developing a fully sustainable agricultural model. This will involve the development of a hybrid energy system to ensure a stable energy supply and the implementation of advanced water purification processes, capable of providing water of sufficient quality for crop irrigation. The use of modelling tools such as computational fluid dynamics will be essential to improve the design and performance of the membrane unit, with the objective of increasing the overall efficiency of the water capture process. Additionally, a digital twin system will be developed for performance monitoring, as well as to simulate potential scenarios and operate in real-time, aiming to optimize process performance, reduce energy consumption and maximize yield in both water production and crop output. The research outcomes will have significant implications, particularly for arid and semi-arid regions, where water scarcity and energy consumption pose substantial obstacles to agricultural productivity.
Requested budget	1,496,650.00 €
Assessment	Not selected to proceed to step 2 (rejected).

4.2 ERC Synergy Grant application

In preparation for an application to an ERC Synergy Grant, Sol2H2O Senior Researchers (SR) started a discussion at the Sol2H2O Project Meeting #4 (September 2024) and #5 (February 2025) around the following topics:

- who will be the Principal Researcher on UNIPA side: Andrea Cipollina;

- who will be the Principal Researcher on UEVORA side: Pedro Horta (to be confirmed, depending on the topic);
- who will be the Principal Researcher on the CIEMAT side: Guillermo Zaragoza;
- who will be the Principal Researcher on ITC side: Antonio De La Fuente;
- what will be the aim of the project: several options were discussed, starting from 1) going beyond SoA of the concept developed in WP2, i.e. sustainable solar desalination and brine mining, 2) selective desalination for agricultural applications, 3) brine mining with advanced post-treatments for high-value products recovery;
- what will be the complementarity of the different Principal Researchers: depending on the topic, a different expertise from each partner should be emphasized;
- what will be the complementarity of the different Research Infrastructures: depending on the topic, a different complementarity strategy should be elaborated;
- inclusion of strong components of services to Industry and technology transfer to market solutions: this was considered not to be relevant for a SyG ERC proposal.

Aiming at having a concept ready for application in 2025 Call, a further discussion has been conducted in the following months via several email exchanges. As an output, UNIPA, in charge of coordinating the proposal preparation, has elaborated a table (see the table below) to collect the key information to start drafting the proposal, aiming at identifying the sub-topics in which each partner can prove to be a major player in the scientific community for low TRL research.

However, all partners have encountered some difficulty in filling the table due to the fact that their research activities and background are mostly based on pilot-scale investigation, rather than low-TRL fundamental research.

Having that in mind, UNIPA has contacted the UNIPA support for ERC proposals preparation (P&F Technology) in order to guide the strategic choices and start elaborating a proposal draft.

After a couple of meetings, in which Andrea Cipollina has presented the idea and asked advice on the feasibility of the proposal for the SyG call, the expert from P&F has provided the following feedback:

“As anticipated in our meeting, we believe that the project is very valid, although not exactly suitable for the ERC Call, but perfectly eligible for a LIFE call.

For this reason, if you deem it appropriate and if the partnership is in agreement, we could consider submitting the project to a LIFE call, we remain available if support is needed.”

Based on the above, and considering that the consortium background is anchored, to a good extent, on research infrastructures supporting activities on TRL 4-6, which renders difficult to present a good proposal on lower TRL levels, as seems to be a requirement for ERC Synergy grants, an alternative plan has also been discussed. Such a plan would entail, as alternatives:

- the preparation of a concept for a UEvora lead application to a HORIZON EUROPE WIDERA Excellence Hub Call. This alternative plan has already been exploited:
 - upon contact with Sol2H2O Project Officer, who confirmed this possibility upon due justification in deviations to the original plan;
 - upon contact with the Portuguese National Contact Point, validating the possibility of using an Excellence Hub proposal as a corollary of Sol2H2O activities in WPs 2, 3 and 4 to the Widening institution, informing that a Call is foreseen for 2027;

- the preparation of a proposal to a suitable LIFE Call, as of the P&F expert suggestion.

A final decision on which proposal to develop within the framework of Sol2H2O will be taken by the Consortium, upon discussion in the Sol2H2O Project Meeting #6 (June'2025) and duly reported and documented in the project final report.

5. SPIN-OFF FACILITY

Standing as a support measure aiming at providing YR with an entrepreneurial path for their careers, seeking a possible commercial exploitation or research results, the Sol2H2O Spin-Off facility provided both Candidate and Young Researchers with guidance and support in the creation of Spin-off companies. Considering the different aspects pertaining to this process, materials on legal, financial, specific measures for IP protection (patents or other forms of protection) and fiscal aspects, besides an overview of the framework of Spin-offs at their different development (and financing) stages have been prepared in an internal cooperation, at the Widening institution, with the Innovation and Entrepreneurial office of the University of Évora (DIC2E).

A first seminar on the Spin-Off facility took place in the 3rd Sol2H2O meeting (Palermo, January 2024). In this Seminar, a presentation on “Empowering Entrepreneurship: The Role of Spin-off Facilities” has been presented, including topics such as:

- Innovation stages - from Idea to Monetization - Ideation, Validation, Protection, Market;
- Ideation - identifying a problem, its solution and whether it has a competitive advantage;
- Validation - proof of concept (a demonstration to validate an idea), prototyping and usability test, market pool (potential customer base) and business model;
- Protection - different ways of protecting an idea or technology: patent, utility model, brands, design, trade secrets and copyright (differences between them were explained by using an umbrella with different innovations as an example);
- Market - public support to investment (how to find them), training in “elevator pitch” and how to approach Venture Capitals and Business Angels, and exit strategy for investors.

Figure 5.1: Exemplary contents of Spin-Off facility materials

Aiming at mapping the available resources, both internally and in the Widening region, supporting the different stages of a spin-off creation, UEvora developed an innovation assets matrix to be continuously updated throughout the project and enabling the identification of gaps and needed improvements.

Research Sub-Topic	Mg-crystallisation	Transport phenomena in Ion Exchange Membranes	hydrothermal or electrochemical reduction of M(OH) ₂ powders recovered from brines into metallic Magnesium adopting solar energy
TRL	3 - 6	2-4	2-3
background	lab- and pilot-scale activities in several EU projects focusing on the recovery of high-purity Mg(OH) ₂ from brines	fundamental research on how single ions are transported in membranes, relevant for the selective recovery of species	Work on the lab-characterisation of Mg(OH) ₂ powders produced from brines could be the basis for selecting conditions and processes allowing for the reduction into metallic Mg CIEMAT background in the exploitation of solar energy could be very synergic
bibliographic references	<p>1) Battaglia G., Romano S., Raponi A., Marchisio D., Ciofalo M., Tamburini A., Cipollina A., Micale G., Analysis of particles size distributions in Mg(OH)₂ precipitation from highly concentrated MgCl₂ solutions, Powder Technology 398 (2022), 117106, doi: 10.1016/j.powtec.2021.117106.</p> <p>2) Battaglia G., Domina M.A., Lo Brutto R., Lopez Rodriguez J., Fernandez de Labastida M., Cortina J.L., Pettignano A., Cipollina A., Tamburini A., Micale G., Evaluation of the Purity of Magnesium Hydroxide Recovered from Saltwork Bitterns, Water 15 (2023), 29, doi: 10.3390/w15010029.</p> <p>3) Romano S., Trespi S., Achermann R., Battaglia G., Raponi A., Marchisio D., Mazzotti M., Micale G., Cipollina A., The Role of Operating Conditions in the Precipitation of Magnesium Hydroxide Hexagonal Platelets Using NaOH Solutions, Crystal Growth and Design 23 (2023), doi: 10.1021/acs.cgd.3c00462.</p> <p>4) López J., Battaglia G., Lupo D., Fernández de Labastida M., Vallès V., Luis Cortina J., Cipollina A., Micale G., Integration of ion-exchange and crystallisation processes to recover boric acid and magnesium hydroxide from saltworks bitterns, Separation and Purification Technology, 354 (2025), 129532. Doi: 10.1016/j.seppur.2024.129532</p>	<p>1) De Luca G., Luque Di Salvo J., Cipollina A., Luque G.L., Fuoco A., Leiva E.P.M., Micale G., Vertically aligned carbon nanotubes for monovalent cation selective membranes designed by in silico experiments, Desalination 544 (2022), doi: 10.1016/j.desal.2022.116123.</p> <p>2) Sireci E., De Luca G., Luque Di Salvo J., Cipollina A., Micale G., Prediction of equilibrium water uptake and ions diffusivities in ion-exchange membranes combining molecular dynamics and analytical models, Journal of Membrane Science 668 (2023), 121283, doi: 10.1016/j.memsci.2022.121283.</p> <p>3) Purpura G., Papiewska E., Culcasi A., Filingeri A., Tamburini A., Ferrari M.C., Micale G., Cipollina A. Modelling of selective ion partitioning between ion-exchange membranes and highly concentrated multi-ionic brines Journal of Membrane Science 700 2024 122659 10.1016/j.memsci.2024.122659</p> <p>4) Purpura G., Saif H.M., Culcasi A., Pawlowski S., Crespo J.G., Cipollina A., Modelling selective lithium recovery from brines via membrane flow electrode capacitive de-ionization, Separation and Purification Technology, 364 (2025), 132400. Doi: 10.1016/j.seppur.2025.132400.</p> <p>5) Filingeri A., Philibert M., Filloux E., Brehant A., Tamburini A., Cipollina A., Micale G., Assisted-Reverse Electrodialysis for permeate remineralization from surface water RO brines: Experimental investigation with multi-ionic solutions, Journal of Water Process Engineering, 67 (2024), 106156, Doi: 10.1016/j.jwpe.2024.106156</p>	<p>1) Vassallo F., Morgante C., Battaglia G., La Corte D., Micari M., Cipollina A., Tamburini A., Micale G., A simulation tool for ion exchange membrane crystallization of magnesium hydroxide from waste brine, Chemical Engineering Research and Design 173 (2021), pp. 193–205. doi.org/10.1016/j.cherd.2021.07.008.</p> <p>2) Battaglia G., Romano S., Raponi A., Marchisio D., Ciofalo M., Tamburini A., Cipollina A., Micale G., Analysis of particles size distributions in Mg(OH)₂ precipitation from highly concentrated MgCl₂ solutions, Powder Technology 398 (2022), 117106, doi: 10.1016/j.powtec.2021.117106.</p> <p>3) Battaglia G., Domina M.A., Lo Brutto R., Lopez Rodriguez J., Fernandez de Labastida M., Cortina J.L., Pettignano A., Cipollina A., Tamburini A., Micale G., Evaluation of the Purity of Magnesium Hydroxide Recovered from Saltwork Bitterns, Water 15 (2023), 29, doi: 10.3390/w15010029.</p> <p>4) Raponi A., Achermann R., Romano S., Trespi S., Mazzotti M., Cipollina A., Buffo A., Vanni M., Marchisio D., Population balance modelling of magnesium hydroxide precipitation: Full validation on different reactor configurations, Chemical Engineering Journal 477 (2023), 146540, doi: 10.1016/j.cej.2023.146540.</p> <p>5) Romano S., Trespi S., Achermann R., Battaglia G., Raponi A., Marchisio D., Mazzotti M., Micale G., Cipollina A., The Role of Operating Conditions in the Precipitation of Magnesium Hydroxide Hexagonal Platelets Using NaOH Solutions, Crystal Growth and Design 23 (2023), doi: 10.1021/acs.cgd.3c00462.</p> <p>6) Vallès V., Fernández de Labastida M., López J., Battaglia G., Winter D., Randazzo S., Cipollina A., Cortina J.L., Sustainable recovery of critical elements from seawater saltworks bitterns by integration of high selective sorbents and reactive precipitation and crystallisation: Developing the probe of concept with on-site produced chemicals and energy, Separation and Purification Technology 306 (2023), 122622, doi: 10.1016/j.seppur.2022.122622.</p>

Table 4.3: Key information to drafting ERC Synergy proposal

Action

HR	Creators Product Managers Market Researchers	Prototype Developers Business Analysts (UX) Designers	Legal Advisors (IP) Lawyers	Marketing Team Sales Team PR Specialists
Funding	Research	Workshops	Legal Fees	BA and VC
Tools	Brainstorming Communication	Survey and FeedBack Prototype tools	Legal project manag. Doc. manag. system	Social media management
Facilities	Office/Workspace Labs	Office/Workspace Labs	Office/Workspace	Office/Workspace
Networking	Conferences Incubators	Networking events Customer validation	Ip Network Associations	Investor Networks

Support resources

Resources

HR	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red
Funding	Green	Green	Orange	Orange
Tools	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange
Facilities	Green	Green	Orange	Orange
Networking	Green	Yellow	Orange	Orange

Support resources

Figure 5.2: Innovation Assets matrix approach in Sol2H2O

In view of exchanging experiences and practice, in this scope, with the filling of such matrix has been requested also to TOP partners (CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA), and what needs to be improved or is not available internally.

Resources - CIEMAT

HR	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red
Funding	Green	Green	Orange	Orange
Tools	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange
Facilities	Green	Green	Orange	Orange
Networking	Yellow	Yellow	Orange	Red

Support resources

Figure 5.3: Innovation Assets matrix by CIEMAT

Resources - ITC

HR	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Orange
Funding	Green	Green	Red	Red
Tools	Green	Orange	Yellow	Orange
Facilities	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Networking	Green	Yellow	Red	Orange

Support resources

Figure 5.4: Innovation Assets matrix by ITC

Resources - UNIPA

HR	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red
Funding	Green	Green	Orange	Orange
Tools	Yellow	Orange	Orange	Orange
Facilities	Yellow	Yellow	Orange	Orange
Networking	Yellow	Yellow	Orange	Red

Figure 5.5: Innovation Assets matrix by UNIPA

A final revision of these Innovation Asset Matrices and due discussion on their contents and inter-Consortium cooperation prospects is to be followed upon Project Meeting #6 (June' 2025), as to be reported in the final report.

As to the blueprint for the creation of a spin-off, exemplary of the application of the Spin-off facility assets, the Upgraded and Distributed Facility resulting from WP2 will be the object of study. A business model will be developed to enable the operation of the research infrastructure as an independent service provider. This business model will be part of Sol2H2O D5.2, as part of the updated exploitation plan for the project results.

Stemming from the internal cooperation on this topic within the Widening institution, a regional funding proposal has already been prepared to enable the research facility as a “demosite incubation space”.

A selection of Spin-off facility related materials will be made publicly available in the project Zenodo repository by the end of the project.

6. LIVING AMENITIES FACILITY

Envisaging a comprehensive approach to the creation of attractiveness conditions for research careers by the Widening partner, the Living Amenities Facility (Task 3.4 of WP3), led by UÉvora, aims at the implementation of a support structure rendering the integration of new researchers in the local context easier and welcoming. The Living Amenities Facility covers the “off work” aspects of what renders attractive the Widening context: access to an Excellence Research Infrastructure developing cutting-edge research, having the conditions to feel integrated and able to self-establish with a high life quality standard.

Initially, this facility was based on the creation of a “pre-paid Pass”, but given the legal and administrative obstacles in terms of its financial management faced with the implementation of the Living Amenities Pass (Milestone 12) - how to implement and charge for the pass, who/which department would provide the administrative support to the pass, how to establish further protocols for discounts, and legal constraints related to Public Procurement - the scope of Task 3.4 and MS12 was changed to shift it towards the actions being undertaken to mitigate this problem.

One of the WP3 identified risks was related to Living Amenities WP3 [T3.4]: “Living Amenities pass has no subscriptions”, and a possible response strategy, following D1.1 Quality Assurance and Risk Mitigation Plan, was to reduce it by revising the contents of the Pass and outreach for

discounts. As this risk became an Issue, as the implementation of a Living Amenities Pass faced obstacles, mitigation procedures were taken.

The contingency plan was to foster an alternative solution based on information supply only, and, as a result, a simplified solution was established by the consortium:

- implementing and expanding the Living Amenities assets available on the project website (map with marked points of interest, cultural agenda, useful contacts, etc.);
- implementing a “Mentoring Initiative” scheme, aiming to introduce the city/region and the aforementioned assets helping the newcomers - mentees - to arrive and settle in the region by residents - volunteer mentors (on a first approach, considering researchers and technicians at UÉvora).

- **Living in... on the Sol2H2O website**

On the project website, <https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/>, the menu “Careers” (Figure 6.1) includes the Living Amenities sections that were designated as “Living in [partner's region]”.

Figure 6.1 – “Living in ...” on the Sol2H2O website

The concept of the Living Amenities Facility was developed in the project meetings, and the “Living in Alentejo”, “Living in Sicily”, and “Living in Gran Canaria” (to be implement soon) sections on the Sol2H2O website are implemented not only by the Widening partner UÉvora, but also some of the TOP partners, UNIPA and ITC. All assets on the website are translated into English and the partners' languages, Portuguese, Italian, and Spanish.

“Living in Alentejo” (<https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/living-in-alentejo/>) refers to the Alentejo region, where the University of Évora is located. The Alentejo is the region located in the centre-south of Portugal, and though it has the largest extension, it occupies around a third of the national territory - it is one of the least populated. The Alentejo (the name derives from ‘beyond the Tagus River’) is known for its rural landscape, and historical and cultural heritage. Évora, the main city, is a UNESCO World Heritage Site.

In this website section (Figure 6.2), videos about the region and the Renewable Energies Chair (UÉvora), a map with points of interest was developed (with the contribution of all partners to define which are the main points of interest to be highlighted), a calendar of activities and events in the city of Évora and surrounding area, a link to the University’s welcome guide, a list of useful contacts, and a small dictionary of useful English words translated into Portuguese, are

available.

Figure 6.2 – “Living in Alentejo” on the Sol2H2O website

Following these guidelines, UNIPA implemented content on “Living in Sicily” (<https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/living-in-sicily/>). Sicily, the largest island in the Mediterranean, is an autonomous region of Italy whose capital is Palermo, Italy's fifth largest city and home to UNIPA. Sicily is known for its rich historical and natural heritage and traditions.

In this website section (Figure 6.3), a video about UNIPA and a link to its welcome guide are available.

Figure 6.3 – “Living in Sicily” on the Sol2H2O website

- **Mentoring Initiative**

The Sol2H2O Mentoring Program is active on the project website (<https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/mentoring-program/>, Figure 6.4).

Mentoring Program

We are pleased to announce that the Sol2H2O Mentoring Program is now active on our website! This program offers the opportunity to participate as either a mentor or a mentee in activities outside of work.

If you are interested in signing up, simply fill out the forms available on our website.

Join us!

I want to be a mentor

[Click here](#)

I want to be mentored

[Click here](#)

Figure 6.4 – “Mentoring Program” on the Sol2H2O website

It offers the opportunity to be a volunteer mentor who will help mentees to arrive and settle in the region, in activities outside of work, like finding a house or processing documents. To sign up for the program as a mentor or as a mentored, it is just necessary to fill out a form available on the Sol2H2O website (Figures 6.5 and 6.6), and mentors and mentees will be paired by their schedule availability, language and interests.

Sol2H2O Mentoring Program

This is a form for those who want to be a **mentor** in the Sol2H2O program.

A mentor is someone who helps those who come to Évora to support them in their day-to-day lives, with regard to services, transportation, mobility, etc.

If you are interested, fill in this form.

Name *

A sua resposta _____

E-mail *

A sua resposta _____

Short bio *

A sua resposta

What languages do you speak? *

A sua resposta

What is your availability? (Days/hours) *

A sua resposta

Send us a photo *

Carregue 1 ficheiro suportado. Máximo de 10 MB.

[Adicionar ficheiro](#)

I am aware that the data I provide voluntarily and anonymously is the responsibility of the Sol2H2O project coordinator (lead researcher: Dr. Pedro Horta) and will be stored until the end of the project (2025), in a folder with restricted access to Sol2H2O partners. *

Contacts will only be shared exclusively with Sol2H2O partners (UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA) if authorization to do so is given.

Yes

[Enviar](#) [Limpar formulário](#)

Figure 6.5 – Mentors form

Sol2H2O Mentoring Program

This is a form for those who want to be a **mentored** in the Sol2H2O program.

A mentored is someone who will have a mentor that give support in you day-to-day lives, with regard to services, transportation, mobility, etc.

If you are interested in being a mentored, fill in this form.

Name *

A sua resposta _____

E-mail *

A sua resposta _____

Short bio *

A sua resposta _____

What languages do you speak? *

A sua resposta _____

What are your main needs? (support to find a home, get to know the city, go to a public service, etc). *

A sua resposta _____

Send us a photo *

Carregue 1 ficheiro suportado. Máximo de 10 MB.

[📁 Adicionar ficheiro](#)

I am aware that the data I provide voluntarily and anonymously is the responsibility of the Sol2H2O project coordinator (lead researcher: Dr. Pedro Horta) and will be stored until the end of the project (2025), in a folder with restricted access to Sol2H2O partners. *

Contacts will only be shared exclusively with Sol2H2O partners (UÉvora, CIEMAT, ITC and UNIPA) if authorization to do so is given.

Yes

Enviar [Limpar formulário](#)

Figure 6.6 – Mentoreds form

These forms are available in English, Portuguese, Spanish and Italian (Figures 6.5 to 6.7).

Figure 6.7 – “Mentoring Program” on the Sol2H2O website translated to Portuguese, Spanish and Italian

For the number of registered mentors and mentees, a KPI of 5/15/30 (good/very good/excellent) registrations was defined (maintaining the KPI initially set for Living Amenities Pass subscriptions). At the moment, there are 7 registrations: 4 mentors and 3 mentored, and a mentoring “match” was organised between a CYR from UÉvora (- mentor) and a CYR from ITC (- mentored) during the short-term mobility within the framework of Task 3.2 - Tutoring (WP3), in Évora.

- **Further activities**

In addition to possible updates to the “Living in...” sections on the Sol2H2O website and the continuation of the mentoring initiative with further registrations and matches, other activities have been planned, such as “round a coffee” social events and cultural visits. These activities will be organised by UÉvora to integrate and improve the experience of researchers or other staff coming to UÉvora, if these newcomers come (particularly if for long-term stays), either during the project period or beyond it, as this good practice is now established within the team.

7. IMPACT

Besides the impacts produced with the aforementioned support measures on Capacity Building, ERC, Spin-off and Living Amenities facilities, satisfaction surveys among the researchers engaged in Sol2H2O activities have been conducted to better assess individual viewpoints.

The survey mentioned in section 3.2, was applied not only to CYR and YR, but also to Senior Researchers and Technical/Administrative staff, with a total of 16 answers. Table 7.1 presents some of the more relevant questions answered by the Sol2H2O team.

Table 7.1: Sol2H2O team answers to the satisfaction survey (M22).

Question	Classification (out of 5)
How satisfied are you with Sol2H2O research?	4,75
How satisfied are you with the support for career development at your institution?	3,75
How satisfied are you with the Sol2H2O Research Infrastructure?	4,50
How satisfied are you with the Sol2H2O team?	5,00
How satisfied are you with Sol2H2O in general?	4,75

During the period of the project, visits to the Research Infrastructure were also promoted (apart from the visits during Sol2H2O events, e.g. FTS, Regional Specialization Forum, Water-Energy

Strategy Symposium), with visitors from the Academia, Policy and Industry to PECS - Solar Concentrators Testing Platform (University of Évora).

Some of the visits that took place were from: Portuguese Environmental Agency (ca. 25 visitors) in May'2024; Faculdade de Engenharia da Universidade do Porto (FEUP), Águas do Douro e Paiva, and SIMDOURO (8 visitors) in June'2024; Development of the targeted Educational program for Bachelors in Solar Energy (DEBSEUz) project partners (ca. 20 visitors) in November'24, and Conterol in February'25 (2 visitors) (Figure 7.1).

Figure 7.1 - DEBSEUz project partners visit to PECS (November' 2024)

All public content of Sol2H2O is available on the project website, www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt, including news, deliverables, scientific publications, FTS materials, etc., and it had, by M29, 1921 visitors (4980 visualisations). From these publications, the video materials (FTS presentations) are available on Sol2H2O YouTube and have 520 visualisations, while scientific papers and FTS presentations are available on Sol2H2O Zenodo and have a total of 1478 downloads.

8. RELATED PLANS (FOLLOWING PM² METHODOLOGY)

Deliverables Acceptance Plan

The management of the formal customer's acceptance of project deliverables (responsibilities, activities and the criteria for the deliverables acceptance) is described in the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan*. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Project Description of Action

The *Project Description of Action* includes the project Work Plan and captures all types of resource requirements, schedules and effort/costs foreseen for the deliverables acceptance activities. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

The Project documents will be stored in a shared drive on Google Drive. The access will be granted by that partner, and each user will have a different access according to their profile, role and responsibility in the project.

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) will have access and editing permissions to all folders in the drive. Project Core Team (PCT) will have editing access to respective WP folders and reading access to the remaining ones. The Project Support Team (PST) will have reading access to WP folders, and finally, the Project Owner (PO) may have reading access to all folders, including legal documents.

In each folder, the latest PDF and Word versions of each document will be available and the previous versions shall be conserved in a separate folder named [versions] until the end of the project.

At the end of the project, each partner will make a copy of the shared folder to be stored in their own organisation's drive, and this must be kept following internal organisational procedures.

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	
2	Project Description of Action (Part A and B) <Grant Agreement-101079305-Sol2H2O-1.pdf>	
3	Deliverables acceptance plan <[08.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Plan.SOL2H2O.16-02-2023.v.1>	
4	Deliverables acceptance note <[29.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Checklist.SOL2H2O.26-05-2023.v1.0.xls>	
5	Amendment Living Amenities <Amendment_Nov24_LA pass-->mentoring program>	
6	D3.1 Fast-Track School materials <SOL2H2O_D_3_1_v2>	